

PROBLEMS OF INTEGRATION OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE COMMUNICATIVE AND METHODOLOGICAL COMPETENCE IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING AT TECHNICAL UNIVERSITIES

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Abstract. *In this article, the problems of integration of foreign language communicative and methodological competence during the process of in foreign language teaching are raised in connection with modern challenges. According to the author scientific understanding of methodological competence is developing in conjunction with the concept of communicative competence. As the author regards, methodological competence can be considered one of the components of communicative competence within the framework of pedagogical communicative competence.*

Key words: *communicative, competence, components, developing, education, FLCC, framework, integration, language, principle.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada chet tilini o'qitish jarayonida xorijiy til kommunikativ va metodologik kompetensiyalarni integratsiyalash muammolari zamonaviy muammolar bilan bog'liq holda ko'tariladi. Muallifning fikriga ko'ra, metodologik kompetensiyani ilmiy tushunish kommunikativ kompetensiya tushunchasi bilan birgalikda rivojlanmoqda. Muallifning ta'kidlashicha, metodologik kompetensiya pedagogik kommunikativ kompetensiya doirasida kommunikativ kompetensiyaning tarkibiy qismlaridan biri deb hisoblanishi mumkin.*

Kalit so'zlar: *kommunikativ, kompetensiya, komponentlar, rivojlanayotgan, ta'lim, FLCC, doirasi, integratsiya, til, tamoyil.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье в связи с современными вызовами поднимаются проблемы интеграции коммуникативной и методической компетенции иностранного языка в процессе обучения иностранному языку. По мнению автора, научное понимание методической компетенции развивается параллельно с концепцией коммуникативной компетенции. Как считает автор, методическую компетенцию можно рассматривать как один из компонентов коммуникативной компетенции в рамках педагогической коммуникативной компетенции.*

Ключевые слова: *коммуникативный, компетентность, компоненты, развитие, образование, FLCC, структура, интеграция, язык, принцип.*

The problem of integrating education and science is not new; it highlights the path that, in principle, the entire world is following. However, global scientific circles have not yet resolved the need for this path for all countries; the pros and cons must be weighed. “On the one hand, integration contributes to: - increasing the effectiveness and efficiency of research; - improving the quality of education and training of scientific and technical personnel, the efficient use of budgetary funds, activating interactions with business, and the commercialization of applied research and development results; - an influx of young people into research and development, etc” [3].

Ensuring meaningful integration in the continuous linguistic and methodological training of foreign language teachers at a university is based on identifying its mechanisms, preliminary differentiation of the competencies developed during the training process, and their refinement in line with the principles of methodological science. “We are convinced that foreign language communicative competence (FLCC) encompasses not only a wealth of knowledge and skills, but also practical foreign language communicative experience, as it views the object not from the perspective of a given, which is understood as an individual's linguistic ability, but from the perspective of the purposeful process of developing the linguistic identity of a bilingual student and a monolingual (or bilingual) pupil” [4]. Moreover, the acquisition of professional FLCC by a future foreign language teacher must be accompanied by the acquisition of methodological competence, which includes the knowledge, skills, and ability to practically implement them necessary for the implementation of methodological activities. “On the threshold of a new century the socio-cultural context of learning foreign languages has significantly changed in Uzbekistan. Their educational and self-educational functions at schools and institutions of higher education significantly increased, professional value in the labor market as a whole, which resulted in increased motivation in the learning of languages of international communication. Respectively increased and needs to use foreign languages” [1]. New challenges include changes in the requirements for language proficiency, identification of new approaches to content selection and organization of material. “The content of modern education in schools, in higher educational institutions is determined by communicative goals and objectives in all stages of training, where training is directed on development of communicative culture and socio-cultural education, enabling them to be equal partners in intercultural communication in a foreign language in everyday, cultural, educational and professional spheres’ [2]. Foreign language, thus, as a tool for learning in terms of communicative-oriented teaching is also a means of social and cultural education. Communicative-oriented teaching of foreign languages, in our case English, means the formation of students’ communicative competence of the language, colloquial, practical, social linguistic and thinking, when the student is ready to use a foreign language as an instrument of intellect activity.

“The process of direct realization of the language system and regulations in practice came into the center of attention of linguists. It became clear that the operation of language in communication is not an abstract rule or system, but those options, which are presented at speaking, listening, reading and writing in everyday communication’ [4]. The object of the research was, therefore, something in linguistics called speech any written or spoken text. It is important to note that it was considered not in itself, but in the totality of the factors of its generation: who, with whom, how and for what purpose someone communicates. The central concept of pragmatics, and with it the methodology was communicative situation, including all these and other factors affecting the nature, purpose and methods of communication. This resulted in a real revolution in the methodology of language teaching, namely the development and establishment of the communicative approach, the purpose of which was learning to communicate in a foreign language, approximate in their qualities and characteristics to how people use the language of native speakers. Because all operations with language are understood in line with the pragmatic theory as the action, methodical system of the communicative approach considers the learning process as action performed with language. “The content of modern education in schools, in higher educational institutions is determined by communicative goals and objectives in all stages of training, where training is directed on development of communicative culture and socio-cultural education, enabling them to be equal

partners in intercultural communication in a foreign language in everyday, cultural, educational and professional spheres" [5]. Foreign language, thus, as a tool for learning in terms of communicative-oriented teaching is also a means of social and cultural education. Communicative-oriented teaching of foreign languages, in our case English, means the formation of students' communicative competence of the language, colloquial, practical, social linguistic and thinking, when the student is ready to use a foreign language as an instrument of intellect activity. In connection with the development of a pragmatic approach in linguistics the interest in mechanisms of communication through language to its communicative function has increased.

Scientific understanding of methodological competence is developing in conjunction with the concept of "communicative competence. "The implementation of the communicative function in foreign language teaching has been explored in many studies. For example, the works of V.G. Kostomarov and O.D. Mitrofanova, G.A. Kitaygorodskaya, and E.I. Passov substantiate the educational principle of active communication as the leading one in implementing the activity-based speech approach to foreign language teaching, affirming its dominant and integrative role in the classroom" [4]. Communicative competence is recognized by many researchers as a complex whole that cannot be described within the framework of a single theory, as language proficiency and communicative skills involve knowledge of multiple units at different levels, combining complex speech patterns. Currently, the concept of "communicative competence" is acquiring a more synthetic meaning and is beginning to express the overall goal of language teaching, the result of many objectives, defining the core content of the educational process. It is no coincidence that the methodological interpretation of communicative competence in scientific works is usually presented as the primary goal of student preparation and the goal of school education, reflecting societal needs.

Thus, from a methodological perspective, ICC can legitimately be viewed in two aspects: as a task of training a foreign language teacher (in this case, it is a professional and educational ICC) and as the goal of their methodological activity in the professional sphere. In today's world, the competencies that comprise the components of the ICC and reflect the comprehensive goal of foreign language teaching are of primary importance for mastering a foreign language: linguistic, speech, sociocultural, discursive, strategic, and compensatory.

In a methodological interpretation, communicative competence is viewed not so much as a component of linguistic ability as the primary learning objective. This means that its understanding is more closely aligned with the practical tasks of language teaching. Consequently, the choice of its types can vary depending on the specific learning conditions and student needs. Thus, in the context of foreign language teacher training, there is a significant convergence of subject-specific and linguistic competencies, while linguacultural and discursive competencies are significantly expanded. Methodological competence, which is realized in the process of pedagogical communication, should be recognized as no less complex and, therefore, can be considered one of the components of communicative competence within the framework of pedagogical communicative competence.

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